

USE OF THE MANCHESTER PROTOCOL BY NURSES IN URGENT AND EMERGENCY SERVICES

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Introduction: The Manchester Protocol is a screening tool that enables the reception and risk classification of citizens in urgent and emergency care services. It was established as an instrument that seeks to humanize, organize and optimize care through criteria that list imminent risks to life, as well as being a means of qualified listening. **Objective:** To highlight in the literature the use and importance of the appropriate application of the Manchester Protocol by qualified nurses in urgent and emergency services. **Methodology:** This is a literature review carried out between April and May 2023, consulting the Ministry of Health's Virtual Health Library, LILACS, BDENF and Google Scholar databases, using descriptors contained in the Health Sciences Descriptors (DeCS): "Risk classification"; "Nursing"; and "Reception". To prepare the review, 11 scientific studies were selected using inclusion and exclusion criteria, all of which were in Portuguese. The criteria used to select the studies were: articles published in the national literature focusing on the use of the Manchester Protocol by nurses, published between 2018 and 2022. **Results:** It can be seen that nurses working in urgent and emergency care need a qualified eye and comprehensive clinical knowledge, being able to interpret the flowcharts of the Manchester Protocol and conduct situations of distress that require rapid decision-making during the triage of users arriving for care. The implementation of this protocol is of great importance, since it is the responsibility of nurses, who have the autonomy and legal backing to assist highly complex cases, as well as providing continuity of care for patients. In addition, the fundamental role of the nursing professional as manager in articulating and maintaining the organizational flow of the service is evident, through the systematization of care in the careful evaluation and establishment of priorities, making it resolute. **Conclusion:** As a result of the aspects mentioned above, we can see the importance of risk classification in urgent and emergency care units, which, linked to the training of the professional nurse, promotes better management of users' needs and prioritization of high-risk clinical conditions. This highlights the sensitivity and skills of nursing professionals in directing care and minimizing harm.

Keywords: Risk classification. Nursing. Reception.

Subject Area: Reception and risk classification.